

Role of Hormonal Therapy (Human Chorionic Gonadotropin – HCG) in the Management of Cryptorchidism

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Abstract

Background: Cryptorchidism is a congenital anomaly characterized by the failure of one or both testicles to descend into the scrotum at birth, and manual repositioning is not feasible. Its etiology is multifactorial, involving genetic, hormonal, and anatomical components. The condition is associated with an increased risk of infertility, testicular malignancy, torsion, and inguinal hernia (>90%), in addition to cosmetic concerns. Early and appropriate treatment is therefore crucial. **Aim of the Study:** This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness, benefits, and potential risks of hormonal therapy in the management of undescended testes. **Patients and Methods:** A prospective study was conducted at the Central Child Teaching Hospital in Baghdad from October 2012 to February 2015. A total of 100 patients with 122 undescended testes were enrolled. Patients were divided into two groups: Group A (control, 30 patients) underwent surgery without hormonal treatment; Group B (study, 70 patients) received HCG therapy prior to surgery. Group B included 86 undescended testes (32 bilateral, 54 unilateral; 38 impalpable, 48 palpable). HCG was administered intramuscularly at 500 IU twice weekly for ages 1–5, and 1000 IU for those older than 5, over five weeks. **Results:** The overall success rate of complete testicular descent was 38.3%, higher in bilateral cases (50%) and palpable testes (56.3%), with best outcomes in ages 4–6 and 7–9 years. Notably, 47.3% of impalpable testes became palpable. After 4 months, the success rate declined to 30.2% due to a 21% relapse. A statistically significant difference ($P < 0.001$) was found between groups. **Conclusion:** HCG therapy is a valuable option for treating undescended testes, particularly in bilateral, prescrotal cases over age 4. It also facilitates surgical management as a neoadjuvant intervention.

Introduction

Cryptorchidism, commonly referred to as undescended testis (UT), is a congenital anomaly where one or both testicles fail to descend into the scrotum at birth and cannot be repositioned manually. The term "cryptorchidism" literally translates to "hidden testicle" and is frequently used interchangeably with "undescended testicle" [1]. This condition affects approximately 1–4.5% of full-term male neonates, with a significantly higher incidence in premature infants (30–45%) [1,2]. While spontaneous testicular descent occurs in many cases—up to 75% in full-term neonates

and 90% in preterm infants—the prevalence of UT declines to about 0.8–1.2% by one year of age [3,4]. Accurate diagnosis and differentiation of UT from retractile, ectopic, or vanishing testes are critical. Ectopic testes deviate from the normal pathway of descent and are typically located outside the scrotal trajectory, often developing normally with fewer associated complications [4]. In contrast, true undescended testes are more likely to be dysgenetic, associated with short spermatic cords, and present a significantly higher risk for infertility, malignancy, torsion, and inguinal hernia (>90%) [5]. Testicular

More Information

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descent is a complex, multi-phase embryological process involving both hormonal and anatomical guidance. The initial transabdominal phase (7th–15th week of gestation) is regulated by insulin-like peptide 3 (INSL3) and its receptor LGR8 [6], while the later transinguinal phase (completed by the 35th week) is androgen-dependent and guided through genitofemoral nerve signaling and gubernacular migration [4,7]. Any disruption in this sequence—whether due to genetic mutation, hormonal insufficiency, anatomical anomaly, or environmental exposure (e.g., maternal smoking, endocrine disruptors)—can result in UT [8]. The etiology may also involve hypothalamo–pituitary–testicular axis dysfunction, Leydig cell underfunction, or androgen receptor defects, often seen in conditions like Prader-Willi or Kallman syndrome [9]. The risk of infertility in UT patients is substantial and increases significantly in bilateral cases. Azoospermia affects 13.3% of untreated unilateral UT patients and up to 88.6% of those with untreated bilateral UT [10]. Shared intrinsic testicular pathology is thought to affect both descended and undescended testes, further compromising fertility potential [11]. The malignancy risk is also notably elevated—between 35 to 48 times higher than the general population—with abdominal testes at the greatest risk [5,12]. Delayed orchiopexy (after age 11) dramatically increases malignancy risk [5,11,13]. Management strategies for UT include both hormonal and surgical approaches. While surgical correction (orchiopexy) remains standard in many countries, particularly the USA, hormonal therapy using agents such as human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) and gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) has been widely employed, especially in Europe since the 1930s [1,14]. Hormonal therapy aims to leverage the physiological mechanisms of testicular descent, particularly through gonadotropin stimulation. However, its efficacy varies based on age, testis position, and treatment protocol. hCG therapy shows success rates between 0–55%, although side effects such as precocious puberty, testicular inflammation, and potential long-term germ cell impairment have been reported [14,15]. Given these factors, this study was conducted to assess the success rate, benefits, and possible risks of hCG therapy in the management of undescended testes. The objective was to determine its clinical efficacy and role as either a primary or adjunctive treatment option in the management of UT.

Method

A prospective study was conducted at the Pediatric Surgery Center of the Central Child Teaching Hospital in Baghdad over a period extending from October 2012 to February 2015. A total of 100 male children, aged between 1 and 12 years, presenting with a diagnosis of cryptorchidism were enrolled. These patients

collectively had 122 undescended testes. A complete history was obtained, followed by thorough general and local examinations conducted in both supine and squatting positions under calm conditions to assess for associated syndromes, ambiguous genitalia, penile anomalies, retractile testes, and scrotal development. Ultrasound examination was performed for all patients, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was conducted for 15 cases where the testes were impalpable and not visualized on ultrasound. Patients with retractile or ectopic testes were excluded from the study. Patients were divided into two groups. Group A (control group) consisted of 30 patients with 36 undescended testes managed surgically without prior hormonal therapy. Group B (study group) included 70 patients (86 undescended testes) who received human chorionic gonadotropin (HCG) therapy. In Group B, 32 testes were bilateral (12 impalpable) and 54 were unilateral (26 impalpable). Based on age, patients in Group B were stratified into two subgroups: 1–5 years (received 500 IU/injection) and 6–12 years (received 1000 IU/injection). HCG was administered intramuscularly twice weekly for five weeks under direct hospital supervision after informed parental consent. Patients were followed clinically for signs of testicular descent, palpability, and adverse effects of treatment during each visit and at the end of therapy. Those with partial or no response underwent open orchiopexy. Fourteen patients with high intra-abdominal testes confirmed by MRI were referred for laparoscopic management to an external center. Thirty patients from Group B who underwent surgery were assessed for surgical difficulty—manipulation time, cord length, and hernial sac dissection—and compared with Group A using the Chi-square test. All surgically treated patients were followed for four months to rule out transient descent.

Results

Out of 86 undescended testes in 70 patients who received hormonal therapy, 33 testes (38.4%) in 27 patients successfully descended into the scrotum by the end of treatment. This included 50% (16/32) of bilateral testes and 31.4% (17/54) of unilateral testes (Table 1). Age-wise success rates were highest in children aged 4–6 years (46.6%), with 66% descent in bilateral and 33% in unilateral cases. In the 7–9-year group, 40% success was recorded (50% bilateral, 35% unilateral), followed by 30% in the 10–12-year group (25% bilateral, 33% unilateral), and 25% in the 1–3-year group (33% bilateral, 20% unilateral). Regarding testis palpability, 47.3% (18/38) of impalpable testes became palpable after HCG treatment. As for testis location, only 15.7% (6/38) of impalpable testes descended: 1/15 high abdominal, 2/10 at the deep ring, and 3/13 high canalicular. Meanwhile, 56.3% (27/48) of palpable testes descended: 45.8% (11/24) from the low canalicular level and 66.6% (16/24) from the prescrotal

position (Table 2). A comparison of surgical outcomes between Group A (control) and 30 patients from Group B who underwent surgery after HCG treatment showed a statistically significant improvement in surgical ease and outcome in the HCG group ($P < 0.001$) (Table 3). After a 4-month follow-up, 21% (7/33) of the initially

descended testes had relapsed, reducing the final success rate to 30.5%. Reported side effects included penile enlargement in 10 patients, pubic hair development in 2, and aggressive behavior in 5—all in children older than 5 years.

Table 1: Response of Undescended Testes (UT) to HCG Therapy in Relation to Age and Laterality

Age Group (Years)	Bilateral UT	Descent Occurred (n)	Descent %	Unilateral UT	Descent Occurred (n)	Descent %	Total Patients	Overall Descent %
1–3	6	2	33%	10	2	20%	13	25%
4–6	12	8	66%	18	6	33%	24	46.6%
7–9	10	5	50%	20	7	35%	25	40%
10–12	4	1	25%	6	2	33%	8	30%
Total	32	16*	50%	54	17	31.4%	70	38.3%

*Note: 4 patients with bilateral UT had descent in only one testis. UT = Undescended Testes.

Table 2: Response of UT to HCG Therapy in Relation to the Site of the Testes

Site	Number	Descent	% per Type	Total No.	Total %
High Abdominal	15	1	6.6%	6	15.7%
Deep Ring	10	2	20%		
High Canalicular	13	3	23%		
Low Canalicular	24	11	45.8%	27	56.3%
Prescrotal	24	16	66.6%		
Total	86	33			38.3%

Table 3: Comparison Between Surgical Outcomes of HCG Treated and Non-HCG Treated Groups

Age (Years)	No. of Patients #	HCG Treated - Adequate Size & Successful Outcome	HCG Treated - Relapse After 4 Months	Non-HCG - Adequate Size & Successful Outcome	Non-HCG - Relapse After 4 Months
1–3	6	5	1	4	1
4–6	10	10	1	9	2
7–9	11	11	—	10	1
10–12	3	3	—	2	1
Total	30	29 (96.6%)	2 (6.9%)	25 (84%)	5 (16.6%)

Note: *6.9% and 16.6% relapse is out of successful outcome of orchiopexy. # The number of patients in each group was 30 (Total = 60). ^ Applying chi-squared test ($X^2 = 2.96$, $DF = 1$), thus $P < 0.001$ (highly significant). It is inferred that with HCG, the outcome is significant. 1 of 30 patients in the HCG-treated group had difficult surgery, whereas 5 of 30 patients in the non-HCG group had difficult surgery.

Discussion

Cryptorchidism remains one of the most frequently encountered congenital anomalies in pediatric urology. Its correction is crucial to prevent potential complications such as infertility, torsion, malignancy, and testicular trauma [1]. The choice between surgical and hormonal treatment is guided by several factors including the age of the patient, testicular position, laterality, and the availability of resources. While surgery remains the first-line treatment in the USA, hormonal therapy—especially with human chorionic gonadotropin (HCG)—has been widely employed in

Europe since the 1930s [1,14]. Hormonal therapy targets the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis, stimulating Leydig cells to produce androgens which in turn facilitate testicular descent. The use of HCG, despite ongoing controversy regarding its efficacy, offers a non-invasive alternative with some success particularly in distal palpable testes. However, anatomical abnormalities such as short spermatic cords or abnormal testis-epididymis fusion may limit the effectiveness of hormonal therapy [16]. In our study, the overall success rate of HCG-induced testicular descent was 38.3%, with a higher rate observed in

bilateral cases (50%) compared to unilateral (31.4%). These findings are consistent with those of Ingerslev (1991), who reported a 50% descent in bilateral and 35% in unilateral cases following HCG treatment [17]. Our results also align with findings from Marchetti et al. (2012) and Kucharski et al. (2013), who reported success rates of 33–53% and 44.5%, respectively [18,19]. Similarly, Aycan et al. (2006) and Esposito et al. (2003) found success rates of 66.7% and 34.5% [9,20]. Age played a critical role in treatment response. We observed peak efficacy between ages 4–9 years, with success rates of 46.6% (4–6 years) and 40% (6–9 years). These results are comparable to studies by Miller et al. (2003), de Muinck Keizer-Schrama et al., and Bierich, who found optimal responses in children aged 2–12 years [21–24]. Moreover, HCG therapy improved palpability, with 47% of previously impalpable testes becoming palpable—similar to Bukowski's 80% and Timothy's 80% conversion rates [25,26]. Location of the testis also influenced success. Prescrotal and low canalicular testes responded best, with descent rates of 66.6% and 45.8%, respectively. Impalpable testes showed lower success (15.4%), consistent with the findings of Lala and Orkiszewski [27,28]. Relapse occurred in 21% of initially descended testes, lowering the final success rate to 30.5%. This is in line with Bertelloni's findings of an 18.9% success and 23.3% relapse [14]. Preoperative HCG improved surgical conditions, making orchiopexy easier by increasing testicular volume and vascularity, a benefit supported by Timothy (2001), Polascik (1996), and Urban (1986) [25,29,30]. Side effects were mild and included penile enlargement (14%), pubic hair (2.8%), and behavioral changes (7%), predominantly in children over 5 years—comparable to the findings by Piotr et al. [19]. Overall, our results support the use of HCG as an adjunct or alternative to surgery in appropriately selected cases.

Conclusion

HCG is effective for treating palpable canalicular and prescrotal undescended testes, especially in children aged 4–9 years. It shows higher success rates in bilateral cases and aids in testis enlargement and palpability. Preoperative HCG improves the ease and success of orchiopexy. Surgical outcomes are significantly enhanced with prior HCG therapy.

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